

IMPORTANCE AND METHODS OF FORMATION OF INDEPENDENT LEARNERS

Turayeva Muborak Abduhamidovna,
o'qituvchi, Jizzah davlat pedagogika universiteti

Abstract: An independent learner does his own research and asks questions, rather than relying solely on materials provided by his teacher or tutor. He also takes ownership of his own learning path by setting his own goals and tracking his progress. This article summarizes the information about the significance of being an independent learner and ways of forming an independent learner, and it is structured on the basis of materials available today.

Keywords: independent learner, autonomous learner, tangible goals, cognitive skills, digital skills, artificial intelligence, innovative era

Annotatsiya: Mustaqil o'quvchi faqat o'qituvchi tomonidan taqdim etilgan materiallarga tayanmasdan, o'zi tadqiqot qiladi va savollar beradi. Shuningdek, u o'z maqsadlarini belgilash va taraqqiyotini kuzatish orqali o'z ta'lim yo'liga egalik qiladi. Ushbu maqolada mustaqil o'quvchi bo'lishning ahamiyati va mustaqil ta'lim oluvchini shakllantirish yo'llari haqidagi ma'lumotlar umumlashtirilib, bugungi kunda mavjud materiallar asosida tuzilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: mustaqil o'quvchi, avtonom o'quvchi, aniq maqsadlar, kognitiv qobiliyatlar, raqamli ko'nikmalar, sun'iy intellekt, innovatsion davr

INTRODUCTION

The implementation of reforms in the social, economic, cultural, and spiritual spheres in our country since the first days of independence have set many important tasks for the education of the youth of our great country, who are mature in all respects, physically strong, competitive, and intellectually capable. This requires, first of all, comprehensive education of the future generation from a spiritual and moral point of view, to have modern knowledge, a broad outlook,

and faith in them. Because the future and prospects of our country depend on the education of this young generation.

Nowadays, the task of independently searching for and learning knowledge according to the requirements of the state educational standard is one of the most pressing problems. Therefore, the importance of being an independent student is one of the most urgent issues in our national education system.

Independent learners have strong ‘affective skills’ which refers to the ability to manage feelings – the most important of which is the ability to delay gratification⁷⁸.

In the more recent higher education white paper ‘The Future of Higher Education’, lifelong independent learners are regarded as essential to meet the needs of the economy and address the ‘productivity gap’ at a time of rapid social and technological change: Today’s generation of students will need to return to learning – full-time or part-time – on more than one occasion across their lifetime in order to refresh their knowledge, upgrade their skills and sustain their employability. Such independent learners investing in the continuous improvement of their skills will underpin innovation and enterprise in the economy and society.’ (DFES 2003, p. 16)⁷⁹.

Hence, independent learning has been set up as valuable for both the individual and society. Education both produces this independence and also, at the higher levels, requires it, with higher education students in particular expected to be independent learners. The following reasons: interchanging educational practices, contexts, and funding, including the development of a ‘mass’ system of higher education with greater reliance on resource-based, online, blended and distance learning involves greater levels of independent study.

Being an autonomous learner has great benefits for the student and society and there are many useful benefits of being an independent learner. Here are some

⁷⁸ Carl Hendrick. Author and Teacher. Dr Carl Hendrick is the author of several books on teaching and learning, including *How Learning Happens* (2020).

⁷⁹ Carole Leathwood Institute for Policy Studies in Education, London Metropolitan University, 166-220 Holloway Road, N7 8DB, London, UK

of the most important and prominent benefits of it. Firstly, it is a skill that is highly valued at university and in the workplace and is vital in life preparation. This skill and associated benefits will remain invaluable while the world will change. Second, it will enable students to feel in control of their academic studies, hence reducing stress, increasing well-being, and leading to improved academic performance. Next, it will enhance student organization and the ability to set tangible goals which will increase student motivation and confidence. In addition, it will enable teachers to provide differentiated tasks. It is consistent with our philosophy on coaching. It will develop resilience for academic purposes and beyond. As you can see, there are many benefits to being an independent learner.

To be a successful independent learner student must develop the necessary organizational skills to work towards independence. In order to thrive in an independent learning culture, they must develop the necessary motivation and confidence. Students will learn how to collaborate effectively in a meaningful way. At the same time, there is a critical balance for teachers to establish between using subject-specific expertise and challenging students through effective and powerful questioning and dialogue. Positive relationships between teachers and students are based on trust and mutual responsibility for learning. Marking is not the same as feedback. The quality of feedback is fundamental to the success of independent learning. Students will need to learn cognitive and metacognitive skills. Teachers will all need to develop the ability to ask the right questions to elicit independent thinking.

In order to develop independent learners in today's modern life, we need to know the main characteristics that belong to them. According to Dr. Carl Hendrick⁸⁰, independent learners are firstly well organized with a clear sense of success criteria for each subject unit. They have a positive relationship with their teachers and tutors and ask for help and guidance when needed. We know that independent learners have developed a robust set of digital skills to enable them to

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use technology and navigate the Internet in a discerning and critical manner. Independent learners focus less on poor revision techniques such as the storage of information (re-reading/highlighting) and more on the generation of questions and answers themselves through self-quizzing/regular low stakes testing. Many of them are able to evaluate exemplar material from their peers or from the exam board to reflect and improve on their own work. They have strong self-regulation and metacognitive skills and are deeply reflective about their individual strengths and weaknesses. Independent learners have an intellectual curiosity bolstered by a wide range of extra-curricular activities. Independent learners have a well-developed capacity for intrinsic questioning as opposed to extrinsic questioning. Independent learners are empowered, unstressed, and in control.

We know that the learners we currently educate will enter a world of work that is shaped by wide-ranging innovations in areas such as artificial intelligence, augmented reality, and robotics. Therefore, we must use the latest modern methods in raising successful independent learners and we can rely on the following ways:

- Encourage goal setting
- Encourage a sense of purpose
- Encourage collaboration
- improved academic performance;
- increased motivation and confidence

If learners set their main goals, they can be able to create targets that they would like to work on independently and achieve in a given limited time. This boosts success as students will feel a stronger sense of enthusiasm towards accomplishing their personal goals as they know the gains will benefit them. Moreover, setting goals helps activate new behaviors, helps, guides their focus and promotes a sense of self-mastery that helps them sustain that momentum in life.

So, in today's rapidly changing innovative era, the role of teachers plays an important role in helping our young people find their rightful place in independent life. Therefore, we need to always show our young people a reasonable, correct,

and clear path by encouraging them to self-reflect and set challenging yet realistic goals. Once students reach this stage of independence, they will have developed key skills necessary to succeed academically and beyond.

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ONLINE EDUCATION: WHAT OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES DOES ONLINE EDUCATION PRESENT IN THE FIELDS OF HUMANITIES AND FOREIGN LANGUAGES? HOW CAN TEACHERS ADAPT THEIR TEACHING METHODS AND ASSESSMENT FOR ONLINE FORMATS?

Usmanova Khilola Ulugbekovna

3rd year student of National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek.
Uzbekistan, Tashkent.
uhilola111@gmail.com

Annotation: This thesis explores the possibilities and challenges of online education in the realm of humanities and foreign languages. It highlights the benefits of increased accessibility, diversity, and personalized learning experiences that online education offers. It also addresses concerns such as the potential lack of face-to-face interaction, the need for self-motivation and technical skills, and the